

RESOLVING SYSTEM OF DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

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Annotation. This paper mainly used moment equations along the longitudinal, transverse and x, y axes. In this system of six differential equilibrium equations, the force coefficients are calculated as seven. Taking into account the system of equations (1), the system of linear equations was reduced to five equations. After finding the components of deformation from the system of equations (5) - (8), the forces in the state of deformation are found using elasticity relations (1). If we accept $\beta = k_z$, then (5)-(7) are translated into a system of four equations for an open profile rod.

Keywords: deformation, longitudinal force, shear force, moment, pipe, equation, differential, curve, bending, load, elasticity.

In [2], a system of six differential equilibrium equations is given that generalizes the well-known Kirchhoff-Clebsch equations. However, for the seven force factors included in

$$\begin{aligned}
 N &= \int_{(s)} \sigma_z \delta ds = EA\varepsilon; \quad M_x = \int_{(s)} \sigma_z y \delta ds = EJ_x k_x; \\
 M_y &= -\int_{(s)} \sigma_z x \delta ds = EJ_y k_y; \quad Q_x = \int_{(s)} \tau_{zx} \delta ds = -EJ_y k'_y; \\
 Q_y &= \int_{(s)} \tau_{zy} \delta ds = EJ_x k'_x; \quad B_\omega = \int_{(s)} \sigma_z \omega \delta ds = -EJ_\omega \beta'; \\
 M_z &= \int_{(s)} \left[(x - a_x) \tau_{zy} - (y - a_y) \tau_{zx} \right] \delta ds + L = M_\omega + L = -EJ_\omega \beta'' + G\bar{J}_d k_z.
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

An additional equation is needed in the form of a connection between the functions $\beta(z)$ and $k_z(z)$, obtained on the basis of some static (or energy) considerations

involving kinematic assumptions, see, for example, [2, 4, 5]). This connection has the form

$$\begin{aligned} \beta &= (k_z \lambda - M_z / GJ_H) \mu; \quad \lambda = 1 + J_k / J_H; \\ \mu &= 1 - J_d / J_H; \quad J_H = \int_{(s)} h^2 \delta ds. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Here J_H – is the “directed” moment of inertia (h is the perpendicular lowered from the center of torsion to the tangent to the section contour element); The geometric characteristics of the J_k, J_d section are given by the formulas

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_d &= M_d / \Omega \delta(s); \quad M_d = GJ_d k_z; \quad J_d = \rho \Omega \\ \tau_k &= 2M_k n / J_k; \quad M_k = GJ_k k_k; \quad J_k = (1/3) \int_{(s)} \delta^3 ds \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

When $\delta_s = 0$ the cross section becomes open. In this case, we can neglect the shift in the middle surface, i.e., take $GJ_H = \infty$. Considering that in this case, that $J_d = 0$ and, therefore, $\mu = 1$ (in addition, $\lambda \approx 1$), from

$$\begin{aligned} \beta &= (k_z \lambda - M_z / GJ_H) \mu; \quad \lambda = 1 + J_k / J_H; \\ \mu &= 1 - J_d / J_H; \quad J_H = \int_{(s)} h^2 \delta ds \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

we obtain a measure of deplanation according to theory [3]: $\beta = k_z$ – for curved rods or $\beta = \theta'$ – for rods with a straight axis.

The above-mentioned system of equilibrium equations was reduced in [2] taking into account (1) to a system of five equations of resolving linearized equations (in accordance with the four components of deformation $\varepsilon, k_x, k_y, k_z$ and the deplanation measure β). For $R = const$ this system has the form

$$(EA\varepsilon)' + k_x Q_y^0 + (Q_y / R) \sin \psi - k_y Q_x^0 - (Q_x / R) \cos \psi + q_z = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$(EJ_x k_x)'' \pm (k_y M_z^0)' \pm \cos \psi (-EJ_\omega \beta'' + G\bar{J}_d)' / R + k_z Q_x^0 - k_x N^0 - \\ -(EA/R) \sin \psi \mp k_z (M_y^0 \pm a_x N^0) \mp \beta' (M_y^0 \pm a_x N^0) \mp a_y (EA\varepsilon)'' + \\ + (m_x \mp a_y q_z)' \pm q_y = 0, \quad (x \leftrightarrow y, \sin \psi \leftrightarrow \cos \psi); \quad (6)$$

$$(EJ_\omega \beta'' - G\bar{J}_d k_z)' - [\sin \psi (EJ_y k_y + a_x EA\varepsilon) - \cos \psi (EJ_x k_x + a_y EA\varepsilon)] \\ / R - k_x (M_y^0 + a_x N^0) + k_y (M_x^0 - a_y N^0) - \underline{k_z D}' - \underline{\beta' D} - m_z = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$k_z = \beta - EJ_\omega \beta'' / \mu GJ_H. \quad (8)$$

The symbol $\leftrightarrow$ in (6) and below means that the lower sign corresponds to a similar equation obtained by mutual replacement of the indices x, y and the functions $\sin \psi, \cos \psi$. In (7) it is indicated:

$$D = i_a^2 N^0 - 2\beta_x M_y^0 + 2\beta_y M_x^0 + \beta_\omega \beta_\omega^0, \quad (9)$$

Where

$$i_a^2 = A^{-1} \int_{(s)} (x^2 + y^2) \delta ds + a_x^2 + a_y^2; \beta_x = (2J_y)^{-1} \int_{(s)} (x^2 + y^2) x \delta ds - a_x; \\ \beta_y = (2J_x)^{-1} \int_{(s)} (x^2 + y^2) y \delta ds - a_y; \beta_\omega = J_\omega^{-1} \int_{(s)} (x^2 + y^2) \bar{\omega} \delta ds. \quad (9a)$$

The transverse forces included in equations (5), (6) are determined by the formulas

$$Q_x = \mp (EJ_y k_x \pm EA a_x \varepsilon)' + \sin \psi (GJ_d k_z - EJ_\omega \beta'') / R + k_x M_z^0 \mp m_y - a_x q_z; \\ Q_x^0 = \mp (M_y^0 \pm a_x N^0)' + (M_z^0 / R) \sin \psi \mp m_y^0 - a_x q_z^0; \quad (x \leftrightarrow y, \sin \psi \leftrightarrow \cos \psi) \quad (10)$$

a_x, a_y – coordinates of the bend center.

In all equations, the superscript “zero” means that the corresponding forces are related to the axes of the undeformed state; forces in a deformed state are determined from elasticity relations (1) after finding the deformation components from the system of equations (5) - (8). Loads q_i, m_i ($i = x, y, z$) are assigned to the

axes of the deformed state (q_x, q_y are applied to the axis of the bending centers, q_x – to the axis of the centers of gravity); q_i, m_i are expressed through the corresponding loads specified in the axes of the undeformed state (q_i^0, m_i^0) using the formulas

$$q_x = q_x^0 l_1 + q_y^0 l_2 + q_z^0 l_3, \quad m_x = m_x^0 l_1 + m_y^0 l_2 + m_z^0 l_3. \quad (11)$$

Expressions for q_y, q_z, m_y, m_z are obtained from (11) by circular replacement of the direction cosines given in

$$\begin{aligned} l_1 &= 1, \quad l_2 = 0, \quad l_3 = -u' - (w/R)\cos\psi \\ m_1 &= -l_2, \quad m_2 = 1, \quad m_3 = -v'' + (w/R)\sin\psi \\ n_1 &= -l_3, \quad n_2 = -m_3, \quad n_3 = 1 + \varepsilon \approx 1. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Note that in equations (6), (7), the terms underlined by one solid line reflect the influence of differences in the inclinations of the fibers, and by two, the difference in their curvature. If we accept $\beta = k_z$, then (5)-(7) go into a system of four resolving equations for open profile rods [1]; if we additionally neglect the underlined terms and put

$a_x = a_y = 0, J_\omega = 0$, then (5) - (7) will coincide with the classical Kirchhoff-Clebsch equations for thin rods. In conclusion, we note that when deriving the system of differential equations (5) - (8), no distinction is made between the radius of the axis of the bending centers and the centers of gravity. This is true under the condition $1 \pm b/R \approx 1$.

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